

ARTICLE INFO

©2026 RS Publication

Paper ID: AJSCS-6969D18270369

Published: 2026-01-17

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18278947>

Page No: 47-64

Resilience in the Face of Decline:

A Study on Fibre Crafts Women Workers, Kerala

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Abstract

Traditional crafts are identified as a vital intangible cultural heritage, with the power to uplift rural communities and preserve indigenous identities. Traditional fibre crafts in Kerala, India, exemplify this synergy for providing livelihoods for rural women. However, despite representing Kerala's cultural heritage, these women workers in fibre crafts are among the most neglected groups in the state. This study assesses the significance of fibre crafts among these rural women workers, examines their perspectives on the craft's decline, and suggests recommendations for their support and sustainability. In-depth interviews with screw pine craft workers in Thazhava, Kollam, revealed that fibre crafts have historically provided social stability, dignity, and cultural identity. Yet, due to economic neglect, undervaluation, lack of governmental support, and challenges with modernization, these women face increasing hardship. Despite their resilience, actionable measures are needed to sustain this craft and uplift its workers, who persevere amidst systemic oversight and limited resources.

Keywords: Women Workers, Fibre Crafts, Decline, Intangible Cultural Heritage

Introduction

Cultural roots are the identity of a citizen of a developing country. Preserving the culture, the non-materialistic asset, through valorizing the knowledge regarding the asset is a tactical strategy for the sustenance of an indigenous community. UNESCO identifies the importance of cultural heritage and the palpable role it plays in a community. In the Article 2 of the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH), UNESCO (2003) calls "*the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artefacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities,*

Cite This Paper: Ganga. P. Sreenivasan and M. Hilaria Soundari (2026). "Resilience in the Face of Decline: A Study on Fibre Crafts Women Workers, Kerala". *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SUSTAINABLE CITY AND SOCIETY (AJSCS)*, vol. 16, no. 1, 2026, pp. 47-64. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18278947>

groups and, in some cases, individuals” as Intangible Cultural Heritage. Transmitting from generations to generations, ICH embalms the history of a land itself.

Traditional crafts are one among the most tangible manifestation of Intangible Cultural Heritage. While the origin of traditional crafts is always traced to an act of survival mechanism, evidences have proven that the traditional crafts promote sustainable development in a community through a dual mechanism. Commercialization of traditional crafts in this networking era is a best way to leave the mark of indigenous communities around the world and as on the other hand promote the development of craftsmen and communities (Zbucnea, 2022). Traditional crafts become the most eco-conscious valorization of knowledge and market, while the threat of climate change exists can also act as a mechanism of resistance. While modern technologies cannot offer all the answers to a dramatically fast-changing environment and traditional crafts play an important role in a more sustainable future (Falk, 2022). Women in the developing nations nurtures of traditional crafts. Often offered with limited work opportunities, women make use of natural traditional crafts for livelihood. Thus, rural women can be made up as the active creators ICH. Nevertheless, recent trends display that globalization poses significant challenges to the survival of traditional forms of crafts (Saha, 2020). While globalization increased cross-cultural interactions and expanded the market for Indian handicrafts, it is questionable whether local artisans can sustain their traditional crafts in the face of free trade and mass production, which may outprice their handmade products (Jena, 2010). When the efforts and craftsmanship go to the traditional crafts call for a reasonable cost, the budget friendly machine-made alternative supply goods a lower cost- one of the ways of death of traditional crafts. Thus, safeguarding attempts should instead concentrate on encouraging artisans, whom majorly are women from underprivileged classes, to continue to produce craft and to pass their skills and knowledge onto others.

Contributions of Intangible Cultural Heritage Around the World

Knowledge is a fundamental resource for creating value at both corporate and regional levels. Research shows that Intangible Cultural Heritage has been playing a major role in social cohesion and engagement as a way of bringing together communities in Europe (Heritage, 2019). A study conducted on the role of intangible cultural heritage in the economy of Austria revealed that the cultural heritage sector significantly impacts its Gross Domestic Product (GDP), largely through tourism, which drives income, job creation, and community development. The direct effects of intangible cultural heritage included boosting local income and employment as well as national identity (Petronela, 2016). Studies based in China described ICH as the savior of the “cultural veins” of the Chinese nation by recognizing the utilitarian virtue of ICH. Intangible culture has been contributing to poverty reduction and improve the well-being of communities, nevertheless accelerating global trends and infusion of cultures created by globalization has been creating threat to the ethnic culture of the nation (Lin & Lian, 2018). A study from Turkey (Akbulut, 2022) put forward possible ways on transmitting ICH from generation to generation and keeping them alive. This is done through the creative process of the intergenerational transmission of intangible cultural heritage elements through teaching practices. Coming to the fore in the curriculum development in harmony with the respect for cultural diversity and intercultural dialogue, the practice emphasis on protecting national consciousness.

Intangible Cultural Heritage in India

Traditional crafts have the long history of rehabilitation of rural population in India, who were largely drawn from the depressed classes during famine and other adverse conditions. Indigenous to the land, most of the crafts works are practiced by women (Abot, 1902). Kantha crafts of West Bengal serve as an exemplary on the positive impact of traditional crafts in developing rural communities. Kantha crafts, has been the serving as a means of livelihood for women, especially after India's partition and the Bangladesh Liberation War. The crafts empowering women, rose to a medium of storytelling, with embroidered motifs reflecting personal and socio-political narratives (Bhardan & Bhattacharya, 2022). Post- Independence, while modern industries of the West tries to spread their wings, artisans of the nation were put forward as the backbone of India's traditional industry (Anandhi & Kawlra, 2018).

- **Caste Bound Dynamics of Indian crafts**

Knowledge regarding traditional crafts is communal, built and shared over generations through collective practice rather than belonging to any single individual. Even when innovations occur, they quickly merge into the shared pool of craft knowledge rather than being patented. This knowledge covers all necessary sensory information—such as color, texture, and smell—critical to producing handcrafted items using adaptable methods that work with non-standardized materials (Ionică, 2022). The knowledge regarding a certain type of craft practiced and transferred by a caste group were only practiced by that caste group. While traditional crafts practice protected the underprivileged communities during harder times, in the current status quo where market is not confined to the characteristic of caste occupations (distinguished and dividing work as per the caste you were born into) transfer of traditional knowledge among caste lineage has several drawbacks. It is not only limiting the opportunities, potential and identity of a person but as well as increases the chance of extinction of a certain craft if not practiced well. When globalization threatens traditional crafts, no legislation exists to safeguard India's intangible cultural heritage beyond Geographic Indications (GoI, 2023). India's over 8 million crafts producers face poverty, limited social services, illiteracy, exploitation by middlemen, low social status, and, in some tragic cases, suicide (Liebl & Roy, 2004).

Fragile Future of Traditional Fibre Crafts of Kerala

Originated in the coastal areas, traditional fibre crafts is a prominent craft sector in the state which have been providing livelihood many women from the economically backward plains of the rural Kerala. Coir, *vetiver* (*Chrysopogon zizanioides*), grass, hay, water hyacinth fibre, banana fibre are used for the fibre crafts production among which the usage of screwpine fibre is the oldest (Pandey & Tiwari, 2023). Screw pine have been present in the yards on the rural Kerala household which often were used as a protective fence due to their sharp edges. Out of poverty women started to make value added products from the pine. While it started as a secondary mode of income generation, the identification of the potential of the crafts, lead to the active production of fibre crafts products (KSID, 2018). Mats made from screwpine rose to be the integral part of rural households valued for their ability to promote spinal health and their suitability for the region's climatic conditions. Natural fibre crafts later developed into the traditional crafts of the rural dalit and backward classes women in Kerala. It helped them to occupy a space in the economic sphere where they, as rural women were not able to enter earlier.

Fig 1: Collection of Screw Pine

Fig 2: Woman worker weaving

Fig 3. Value added Products

While there was a time where every household yard occupied with screw pine crafts products, due to the change in market demands and systematic neglect faced by the women workers involved in these crafts, this intangible cultural heritage of Kerala is being erased. As opposite to west, crafts practiced in third world nations are their socially defining character and a communal vision, each crafts dead, each piece of history is dead (Venkatesan, 2009). Despite being architectures of Kerala's rural identity, they are still beyond the purview of registrations and they remain unorganized. The neglect faced by these workers thus clearly have a double fold impact in the state, as it effects both the cultural and economic facets of rural Kerala.

Methodological Framework

Weighing all the discussed factors, the study aimed to assess the significance of traditional fibre crafts in the lives of rural women workers; to analyze the perspectives of women workers on the decline of the crafts and their ways of navigating this decline and to propose actionable recommendations that support the sustainability and upliftment of the women workers in fibre crafts. A qualitative study was undertaken to gain a deep understanding of the experiences and challenges faced by women workers in the screw pine crafts industry. The primary data collection method consisted of In-depth interviews with five women workers. The women workers were selected from the screw pine crafts cluster located in in the village of Thazhava, in the district Kollam, Kerala. The Directorate of Culture, Government of Kerala identifies this as a screwpine crafts village as part of Rural Art Hub Scheme (GoK, 2019). The village itself derives its name from 'thazha', the Malayalam word for 'screw pine', reflecting the deep historical and cultural roots of screw pine weaving in their lives. The village was selected due to their stout role in carrying forward the traditional fibre crafts for decades that is central to their community's cultural identity. Data was collected from the workers who have been a strong contributor for the crafts. Women workers with over three decades of experience in the industry were specifically selected, as their extensive knowledge and long-term engagement provide a broader perspective and a deeper understanding of the craft.

A thematic analysis was employed to systematically explore the insights gathered from the interviews. This analysis, often known as "experiential" research, aims to fully understand the thoughts, feelings, and actions of participants. Finding patterns in and across data in relation to participants' actual experiences is involved in the process (Clarke & Braun 2017). Transcribed to native language (*Malayalam*), the researcher translated the data to English and carefully coded according to emergent themes. Coding is the process of organizing the material into

segments of text before bringing meaning to information (Creswell, 2014). Each code represented a distinct theme, highlighting key ideas and recurring patterns across the interviews. The identified themes were further analyzed to understand the interrelationships between them. By establishing these relationships, the thematic analysis contributed to constructing a coherent narrative that effectively answers the research questions.

Significance of Traditional Fibre Crafts in the Lives of Women Workers

Women workers in the fibre crafts sector revealed their ties to the crafts are firmly ingrained in their cultural identity, going well beyond its financial worth. The women's recollections and introspection demonstrated how traditional fibre crafts used to be an essential part of their community's way of life, offering a strong sense of social and cultural connection in addition to a means of subsistence. Fibre crafts helped these women for role enhancement which helped them to currently identify them as workers. The women's nostalgic recollections of the heyday of the craft as a time of stability and collective pride best capture this profound cultural resonance. While reflecting on fibre crafts, it was the sense of dignity and nostalgia that stood out—economic, social, and occupational dignity, and nostalgia for cultural heritage and tradition, past stability and prosperity, and social recognition. It was identified that fibre crafts served the role of a catalyst for upholding dignity among these women workers. Dignity is a fundamental feature of a democratic society (Miszta, 2013). Thus, through providing the factors for dignity, the crafts showed its integral role in reinforcing the democratic principle of the nation. It was identified that the dignity resulted by their craft extends beyond monetary value, connecting them to family legacy, cultural preservation, and community respect. Fibre crafts have been providing these rural women with monetary help at the same hand profound sense of worth that comes from being able to sustain oneself and one's family through meaningful work. This impart the women with economic dignity for a rural woman as they are being able to financially provide for the family is one of booster of empowerment.

“Working with screwpine has provided us with not only a means of earning a living but also a sense of pride. It has been a cornerstone of our family's existence and well-being”

-Interviewee 3

For a community whom in the social standards considered yet to be progressive, respect is a profound determinant. Participation in fibre crafts, a social asset which culturally and monetarily uplift a rural community has been providing these rural women with respect and dignity within their community. Women workers disclosed that recognition and validation received by the officials and public is a big motivation of them and facilitated social dignity.

“When I participate in fairs and exhibitions, I receive a lot of recognition and respect. People from all walks of life come to speak with us, express their admiration for our work, and even take photos with us. It's not just the general public; even officials like the agricultural officer acknowledge and appreciate the craft.”

-Interviewee 1

Beyond the monetary and social spheres, the women workers expressed that they experienced dignity in performing the labour of fibre crafts. They feel dignified to identify themselves as fibre crafts workers as they are aware about the role the crafts have in building their cultural

heritage. This intrinsic sense of self-worth resulted through the productive work they do imparted the workers with occupational dignity.

"Working with screwpine has been a way for us to honor our family legacy and keep our cultural practices alive. Seeing that others value and respect our traditional craft provides a deep sense of accomplishment and validation."

-Interviewee 3

Extreme nostalgia was the other significant theme identified associated with fibre crafts. They expressed nostalgia in terms of the cultural identity, past prosperity and the social recognition created by fibre crafts. Traditional fibre crafts have been providing livelihood to majority of the villagers during the prime period of the craft. The interview responses identified a deep sense of nostalgia and saw the respondents relishing in past stability and prosperity and the social recognition they received due their participation in the traditional crafts. Studies identify nostalgia as suffering due to relentless yearning (Sedikides, 2008), relentless yearning for the past. Wildschut et al. (2006) identified the frequently reported trigger is a negative experience. The setbacks the women workers face in the current decline of the crafts, trigger nostalgia. Practice of fibre crafts has been engraved into their culture and identity that the village is called by the name of the craft itself. Respondents revealed that the village name "Thazhava" came from "Thazha" meaning screwpine leaf. However, their nostalgia is etched from discontent, as these very crafts, once integral to the village's identity, have now faded into invisibility.

"The very name of our village, 'Thazhava,' is derived from the thazha plant, highlighting its importance to our community. We are people who have lived with this craft for generations, and it holds a special place in our hearts and heritage."

-Interviewee 2

The women workers recall a period in their lives where their traditional crafts work was recognised. Where there was greater demand for their products, the crafts a major source of their income which was sufficient for them. The women workers express the nostalgia they for their past stability and prosperity. This longing for their earlier economic security aligns with Newman's (2022) findings, which indicate that the negative relationship between nostalgia proneness and well-being is significantly stronger among lower-income households. Due to the dissatisfaction of the current livelihood struggles the women workers are reminiscing about a time of greater financial well-being.

"This is how our village thrived in the past. The craft of working with screwpine was the main reason why people settled and lived in this village."

-Interviewee 2

In the past rural villages, practicing their traditional crafts provided a social recognition to these woman workers. Women workers recall a time where they were treated with high regard and haven't seen fibre crafts as just a way of survival. This historical recognition contributed to a strong sense of positive social identity and created social recognition, reinforcing their value within the community. Verkuyten (2005) notes that individuals prefer to identify with positive social identities, providing a positive self-esteem. This sentimental longing for thier past where they were socially recognized and well acknowledged is distinctly evident among these

women.

"As we go out to collect screwpine, we often encounter locals who are curious about our activities. They frequently ask us, sometimes jokingly, if we are still engaged in this traditional craft. In fact, they recognize the value of our work and sometimes even call us to their fields to collect screwpine leaves for our use, knowing the significance and quality of the material."

-Interviewee 2

Contours of Decline: Perspectives on Resilience

Women workers identify that the crafts which helped them build dignity are in the decline. This craft not only helped them to sustain economically but also bonded them to their community and cultural heritage. Thus, the decline of the crafts makes them disappointed in terms of economic decline, due to the emerging generational disconnect and undervaluation of their craftsmanship. They also point out lack of governmental support they are ought to receive as workers in the state. Occupational health related issues are also their major concerns while they are remaining invisible. Yet, despite these challenges, they continue to harbor a deep love for their craft, which is evident in their strong defensiveness and commitment to preserving its significance. The following discussion elaborates on the perspectives of women workers on the decline of the crafts.

While dignity due to the participation in crafts was a prominent emotion which was reflected in the interviews, the current decline of the crafts has resulted in disappointments among the women workers. A primary reason for their disappointment is the current economic instability. The rural women workers in fibre crafts are informal sector workers who are not protected by fixed wages and benefits. Even though years back when the crafts thrived, the income received was helpful, women workers point out that the wages they receive have substantially decreased due to decline in demand. Their activities were also disrupted by external shocks like the COVID-19 epidemic, and the financial burden is made worse by the inability to obtain assistance like social safety nets or subsidies. They had to stop operations, but they still had bear costs for maintaining a craft cluster, which showed how vulnerable unorganized women workers are in times of crisis.

"Unfortunately, the stability we enjoyed was short-lived. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted everything. We had to close our operations for a year and a half, which severely impacted our income. During this period, we still had to pay the rent for our workspace, which was a considerable financial burden."

-Interviewee 1

Women workers underscore the ongoing disregard they have encountered regarding governmental support and assistance. Although the Directorate of Culture, Government of Kerala, has formally designated this region as a screwpine crafts village under the Rural Art Hub Scheme, the women workers persist in facing systemic exclusion (GoK, 2019). Their unregistered status obstructs access to benefits, financial aid, and skill development programs. The lack of official identification cards not only constrains their prospects for economic stability but also denies them formal acknowledgment as artisans, further marginalizing their contributions to the crafts workers.

"Currently, we don't receive any benefits or support from the government. We do not have access to Employee State Insurance (ESI) and social security benefits. Additionally, we do not have artisan ID cards or official membership that might provide us with recognition or further benefits."

-Interviewee 2

The lack of institutional support exacerbates the challenges they face in sustaining their craft in a rapidly changing world. Traditional crafts are distinct with their manual effort in manufacturing. The intellect behind the creation of traditional crafts makes them invaluable. The knowledge that makes up traditional craft have been accumulated over generations and through the exchange of information between craftsmen (Ionică, 2022). Machines may offer efficiency, but they may fail to replicate the delicate, precise work done by hand. But in the world after globalization where quantity over rides quality, full dependency on manual labour is not a formula for success. Women workers express difficulties in balancing innovation with maintaining the integrity of age-old practices.

Fig 4: Traditional Screw Pine Crafts replaced by Plastic Products in Local Markets

"The idea of incorporating machines into our fiber crafts has been explored, and we have had some assistance in this regard. However, implementing machines into our traditional crafting process has proven to be quite challenging and, in many ways, impractical for our needs. Machines, despite their efficiency in other contexts, do not align well with the specific requirements of our craft. Achieving precision while weaving with machines is difficult and do not accommodate the intricate handwork that our craft demands."

-Interviewee 2

The disregard for the health and well-being of women workers constitutes another significant source of their dissatisfaction and concern. A noteworthy discourse which is often overlooked on traditional crafts workers are their health and well-being. Obsession on authenticity on hand made traditional crafts leave the workers with a position where they can't seek any technical help. Fibre crafts are time-intensive and labour-intensive work which leave the women workers with extreme health issues. Research toward developing technology assistance that might achieve a compromise between cutting labor intensity while upholding authenticity remains lacking, however. The processing of fibre for the production of crafts involves drying and dyeing of the natural fibre using chemicals. Women workers disclose that they employ simple safety measures, such as gloves, but do not have access to more extensive protective equipment, including masks or ventilation during dyeing. There is a need for more comprehensive, safety-focused training that covers all facets of occupational health since the limited training offered does not adequately prepare them to handle the risks associated with their jobs.

"When it comes to dyeing the screw pine fibres, we take some basic precautions to ensure our safety, though they are quite limited. We wear gloves to prevent the paint from getting on our hands, which helps protect our skin from potential irritants in the dye. However, aside from wearing gloves, we do not use masks or other protective gear. I have received on how to handle the materials and dyes, but unfortunately, the training did not cover a comprehensive range of safety measures."

-Interviewee 2

Health care of women workers in informal sector is to be addressed more than usual. These workers tolerate enormous financial and physical difficulties due to limited access to health care. The need to hire transportation in order to get to medical facilities leads to additional costs, often equal to a day's wages, which significantly deters people from seeking care in a timely manner. This dynamic makes health problems worse since employees may put off getting treatment because of the expense. Their tenacity and dedication to their work highlight a lack of institutional assistance that would otherwise mitigate these health and financial difficulties.

"Our health and well-being are closely tied to our ability to work. If we fall ill or face any health issues, we often need to hire an auto-rickshaw to visit a medical facility, which incurs additional costs. This expense can amount to a day's wage, which is a significant burden for us. Despite these challenges, we continue to bear the costs and continue our work as best as we can, demonstrating our commitment to preserving our traditional craft despite the lack of technological support."

-Interviewee 2

The undervaluation of craftsmanship serves as a fundamental factor contributing to institutional neglect within the sector. This devaluation not only diminishes the recognition of skills the women workers but also results in inadequate policy attention and blockade of any resource allocation. Traditional crafts, especially feminized crafts work often face undervaluation of the work done. The reason may be the prejudice that these works doesn't demand much labour as it is done by women but on the contrary the crafts works require skill and labour which cannot be replicated. While women are heavily involved in handicraft production, others view their work as only use-value production (Weber, 2004). Women workers reflects on that the significance embedded in each item are often not reflected in its price, leading to a lack of economic recognition for the workers' efforts.

"The amount of work and skill that goes into each item is immense, but unfortunately, this effort is not always reflected in the price consumers are willing to pay. This extensive process is why our products are more expensive compared to mass-produced plastic goods."

-Interviewee 5

Decline in the fibre crafts has a bigger impact in the social cohesion in the villages. This traditional craft, transferred from one generation to the other has been a significant catalyst for intergenerational bonding in villages of Kerala. Studies showcase that traditional crafts facilitates opportunity for Indigenous communities to immerse in traditions and strengthen the relationship among the generations. Spending time together through crafts or storytelling

helped elders and youngsters form strong bonds. This is strengthened when the elders receive appreciation by the younger generation and when the youngsters took pride in learning their culture (Sydora, 2023). Lack of intergenerational knowledge flow the same time leads to the decline in the practice of fibre crafts and have a gap in the intergenerational bond in the rural villages of Kerala.

"Our older generation, who were once the main practitioners of this craft, can no longer continue due to age and health issues, and unfortunately, the younger generation shows little interest in taking it up."

-Interviewee 1

Apart from the constant display of disappointment, defensive preservation of fibre crafts was identified among the women workers. Some of the women workers appeared defensive to their work. Defensiveness is often a mechanism which comes from extreme pride or insecurity. Firm pride in the traditional work they do and defensiveness due to the constant undervaluation of the work they were identified. These workers view their craft as dignified and valuable. They derive self-worth and respect from their craftsmanship and they defend their honour in the work they do.

"We take great pride in our traditional occupation. There's no reason for us to feel ashamed of it. Each job, regardless of its nature, has its own dignity and value, and this is no exception."

-Interviewee 2

There is a section in society who see participation in traditional occupation is due to lack of good opportunities. There is an undervaluation of traditional crafts seen in the changing times. While there was a time where traditional crafts were a pillar of natural heritage, the undervaluation of the work among many showcase how cultural identities are forgotten. This growing disregard has created insecurity among craft workers, prompting them to adopt a more defensive stance as they struggle to preserve both their livelihood and their heritage.

"People often ask us whether we still engage in fibre crafts, but they do so out of curiosity not disdain. The notion that there might be something demeaning about our work is simply not accurate".

-Interviewee 2

Strategies Employed for Navigating Through Decline

In the face of decline of traditional fibre crafts, the resilience of these women workers is highlighted by their adaptability. They show determination to sustain their cultural practices while navigating modern challenges. Adapting to modern techniques of marketing and widening the crafts knowledge through skill development training programmes, these women display utmost optimism during the face of adversity. Resilience refers to positive adaptation (Herrman *et al*, 2011). Despite the decline of traditional practices and limited market access, these women adapt with resourcefulness and determination, finding innovative ways to adapt to changes and keep their crafts alive. The resilience of women workers in Kerala's fibre crafts sector is evident in their efforts they adapt to sustain.

Screw pine was historically valued for its practicality; people used it for fencing, which made it accessible and widely adopted. Screw pine leaves were used for fibre crafts because of its abundance. But now traditional usages of screw pine shifted which resulted in a hindrance in the availability of these plants. But workers haven't lost their effort to find a strong grounding in the market. Screw pine crafts have a found a grounding in houseboat construction which facilitated more, might open a plethora of opportunities for these women.

"In the past, screw pine was commonly used as a natural fencing material around homes and farms, which made it readily accessible. Nowadays, this practice has largely disappeared, and people are only beginning to reintroduce it. These mats are currently highly valued by houseboat builders, who are among our most frequent and reliable customers. This specific demand has provided a somewhat stable source of income amidst the fluctuating market conditions."

-Interviewee 1

Fig 5: Houseboats making use of Screwpine Crafts promoted by Kerala State Tourism

Women workers have started to modify their methods in reaction to the times and their restricted market reach. To generate sales opportunities women workers have been participating in fairs and exhibitions, exposing the craft to a larger audience. The women workers have also capitalized on the popularity of online platforms such as YouTube, where viewers of their educational films occasionally get in touch with them for training or sales. They are now able to reach a wider audience outside local marketplaces because to their increased digital awareness.

"We participate in various fairs and exhibitions to showcase and sell our products. For instance, during a fair organized by the karshakasamathi of the block, we set up a stall in Kayamkulam. At that event, we managed to sell goods worth 3000 rupees. These fairs are not only opportunities for sales but also for exposure, as officers and other visitors often purchase our products. Our visibility has also increased through digital platforms. People who watch our YouTube videos sometimes reach out to us with inquiries and orders."

-Interviewee 1

Fig 6: Educational Video in Online platform:

<https://youtu.be/-Cl2c-y84g4?si=unzs6N2iG3eg5aiJ>

The women workers have been delivering training programs, organizers equip artisans with

specialized skills that help revitalize the underutilized screwpine industry, creating economic opportunities in local communities. The training sessions support the women workers in navigating modern demands and integrating traditional knowledge with current entrepreneurial needs. They have also been developing digital strategies which extends the reach beyond local borders and reach to more potential bodies of interest.

“Recently, there has been a concerted effort to revive the cultivation and use of screwpine, partly due to the training programs provided to local artisans. Each training session costs 1500 rupees per participant. Our most recent training session took place last month in Vadamkara, and we often receive inquiries from individuals who watch our instructional videos on YouTube.”

-Interviewee 1

Despite financial and technological limitations, the women workers in fibre crafts remain dedicated to sustaining their work, signaling a deep hope for the revival of traditional skills. By persistent efforts they actively work towards keeping the craft alive, displaying belief in the importance and value of these practices. Perseverance drive these women workers even in the face of drawbacks. By willingly absorbing the financial burdens and continuing their work, these women demonstrate a strong commitment to their cultural heritage. Despite of the challenges these women workers shows resilience and dedication to ensuring that these skills are not lost to time.

"Despite these challenges, we continue to bear the costs and continue our work as best as we can, demonstrating our commitment to preserving our traditional craft despite the lack of technological support."

-Interviewee 4

They show unwavering faith in strength of community Support to transform their livelihoods. The crafts cluster was formed when rural women, who used to work in their homes, joined their hands together. The cluster is the result of mutual trust of a community as per them. This mutual trust created a huge impact in thier and their families' livelihood and identities.

"The establishment of this artisan cluster can be credited to an institution called Sargalaya. They sought us out in Thazhava and initiated a training program for 25 of us. This initiative significantly boosted our income, giving me substantial monthly earnings, something I wish could have continued."

-Interviewee 1

Preservation of ICH and Livelihood Promotion of Fibre Crafts Women Workers

The framework developed from the responses of the women workers reveals how rural women in fibre crafts navigate a landscape of economic neglect, undervaluation, and cultural erosion.

Fibre crafts have been identified as a valuable crafts sector in Kerala as they are preserving cultural heritage, stability, social recognition and dignity of all dimensions. But the decline of the crafts has broken their balance of lives. It was identified that the women workers now are not paid well which makes them economically unstable. They face undervaluation of their craftsmanship and also there is a generational disconnect which exists now. While generations bonded on the crafts knowledge: through sharing and learning, there is no flow of that skills and knowledge as the new generation moves far away from traditional works. The results of the neglect can be traced to the lack of governmental support that they should receive. Even though they find ways to sustain through these tough waves through resilience and optimism, there are several measures which can be taken to motivate the women workers, despite the decline of the crafts and the systemic oversight they face.

Recommendations

- Cultural Hubs in villages can be set up to enhance community participation surrounding fibre crafts and to carry out village level activities to strengthen their cultural identity. This will help in reinforcing the social status of fibre crafts in communities. These hubs can act as a local museum to document and exhibit the fibre crafts heritage of the village. These hubs can carry out demonstrations and festivals uprooted in fibre crafts. These hubs can be managed by local panchayaths ensuring decentralized decision

making. Raghurajpur Heritage Village of Orissa has one among this existing model of village hub, where the village museum tells the story of a rural crafts heritage (Kumar, 2015).

- Encourage more cooperatives to bring women workers together. Uniting and working as cooperatives can enhance the bargaining power of these women workers. Better bargaining power give them power to negotiate fair pricing, rising their financial independence and self-respect. This better momentum in the society can increase the visibility and dignity of the women workers.
- Efforts to be taken to increase the registrations of women workers. It is undeniably clear that fibre crafts have been building rural identity among rural women in Kerala yet there is no data available regarding definite number of workers involved in this craft. Local help desks under local panchayats and prominent NGOs can be implemented to facilitate this process. Awareness can be raised on the importance of registration and even incentives for registration can be offered.
- Government can act as middleman for linking companies promoting eco-friendly initiatives with in rural women workers in the crafts. This can aid the women workers in getting access to new production techniques while companies can gain from sourcing these eco-friendly products.
- Provide government subsidies, grants, and incentives specifically for traditional crafts to ensure economic stability for women workers. These measures will help to overcome the neglect the women workers face at the state level. Awareness are to be given to the women workers regarding these aids through local news channels, radio and other local women's groups like *ayalkoottam* (neighbourhood groups).
- Offer low-interest loans or microcredit programs to helping to invest in materials and modern tools. Better quality raw materials and modern tools can help the women to increase the productivity of their labour. This can improve their financial positions as well as can reduce the physical stress of intense manual labour.
- State can build up initiatives to purchase fibre craft products directly from women workers for distribution through state run fairs. State can also assist these women workers in creating a brand for the crafts products and facilitate e-commerce platforms. A cultural branding for the crafts as a sustainable brand can invoke interest among the ecologically conscious buyers' groups as the crafts promote a lifestyle of values.
- State government can integrate fibre crafts into their daily administration to ensure consistent income. Even though coir products are used in the government offices, other traditional crafts like fibre crafts can also be integrated to this. The green protocol of Haritha Kerala Mission of Kerala State government, demands the use of eco-friendly decorations and products such as cloth bags and banners in the offices. Fibre crafts products, as sustainable government can promote the products by being the active users. This measure at the same time creates market as well enhance their social recognition.
- Tourism activities can be promoted surrounding the fibre crafts. Can facilitate homestay and visits to crafts villages so to enhance the exposure to the crafts and its workers. Live demonstrations can be setup to exhibit the intricate fibre crafts production and weaving process which allows visitors to appreciate the skill involved and gain a deeper understanding of traditional craftsmanship.
- Health and safety issues of these workers can be addressed through conducting regular health and safety workshops to raise awareness of occupational health risks and safe work practices. Booklets on occupational health issues in regional languages can be drafted with the help of professionals and circulated among the women workers. Better

accessible healthcare services to address the specific health concerns of fibre craft workers, such as respiratory and musculoskeletal issues can be drafted. Government can facilitate free or subsidized regular health screenings among the women workers.

- Interdisciplinary participatory research can be carried out to identify the gaps and offer solutions to bridge the gap between traditional knowledge and modern innovations in the field of fibre crafts. Participatory research can help to weave region specific training strategies for these women in the field of new design trends, entrepreneurship, digital marketing, and financial management. This approach can help address the issue of undervaluation in the sector.
- A serious lack of awareness on the role of crafts in the cultural heritage of the state is visible. Encouraging the younger generations to learn from experienced artisans can bridge the generational gaps and as well as knowledge gaps, ensuring knowledge transfer within communities. School curriculums can be modified with this aim. School students can visit artisan villages to get in contact with the artisans and their history.

Conclusion

The fibre crafts women workers are a pillar of preserving intangible cultural heritage of rural Kerala. However, these women workers are largely excluded from the process of its heritage creation and safeguarding. The study aimed at highlighting both their struggles and their determinant navigation abilities during the face of adversity. Traditional crafts as per UNESCO's list of ICH ensures their safeguarding with the involvement of concerned local communities who embody them. Recognizing their voices and incorporating their perspectives in safeguarding initiatives are crucial steps towards not only preserving these crafts but also ensuring social equity and support for those who sustain them. By implementing inclusive strategies these fibre crafts women workers can achieve greater economic security, social recognition, and improved working conditions, ensuring the sustainability of fibre crafts industry.

Declarations

Availability of data and material

The interview transcripts can be made available as per the request.

Conflict of Interest

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

Funding

The research is funded by The Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR), New Delhi under the ICSSR Doctoral Fellowship Scheme.

Authors' contributions

Author 1

- Worked for the acquisition, analysis and interpretation of data and drafted the work.

- Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

Author 2

- Made substantial contributions to the design of the work.
- Revised the work critically for important intellectual content and approved the version to be published.

Acknowledgements

The author sincerely thanks the screwpine crafts cluster in Thazhava, Kollam, Kerala, for their time and valuable insights during the interviews.

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